

Alliance Data Officers' Group Meeting

Tuesday 30th of January 2024, 1:30pm to 3pm

This is a summary of the key outcomes and actions from the UK Health Data Research Alliance Data Officers' Group (DOG).

Summary of Actions

Action	Lead
Demonstrate the Innovation Gateway/ Cohort discovery tool functionality in the next Data officers group meeting	Technology Team
HDR UK to explore collaboration with Phil Quinlan and John Nolan to look at timelines for implementing GA4GH Beacon V2 standard to query health data.	Technology Team
Next meeting is scheduled for 08/05/2024. Agenda and meeting invitation will be circulated.	Uwaye Ideh (Alliance Secretariat)

1. Welcome

The Chair (Geoff Hall¹) welcomed all to the Data Officers' Group meeting. He introduced himself and encouraged everyone to introduce themselves via the chat.

2. Alliance update (Geoff Hall)

The chair described the work of the Alliance and provided an update on recent developments. In January, we [welcomed seven new members²](#) taking the Alliance to 100 members ranging from NHS trusts, academic organisations and other public bodies and charities and trade associations.

The chair also summarised the role of the Data Officers Group:

- Bring together data officers and data leads from Alliance member organisations
- Coordinate and develop guidance and policies regarding a range of topics relevant to our data partners, community and ecosystem including data standards, data curation, quality, provenance, ontology and terminology, data priorities
- Discuss standards and best practice for data and drive consensus

¹ Professor of Digital Health, University of Leeds; Honorary Consultant in Medical Oncology, Leeds Cancer Centre; Chief Clinical Information Officer, LTHT; and Chief Clinical Data Officer, HDR UK.

² The new members are: Association of British Healthtech Industries (ABHI), techUK, Centre for Longitudinal Studies (CLS), Action Against Age-related Macular Degeneration (AAAMD), Administrative Data Research UK (ADR UK), MRC Regulatory Support Centre and the Professional Records Standards Body (PRSB).

- Inform prioritisation of activities around data standards

3. Gateway update – Isaac Odiase (HDR UK Gateway Product Owner)

- The [Innovation Gateway](#) is a platform hosted by HDR UK for metadata discovery in Health Data Science. It hosts metadata (not the data set) from many different custodians from across the Alliance and beyond. It also hosts metadata on data use, papers, collections, and tools. The idea is to be a “one-stop shop” for researchers.
- The Technology Team is currently working on the Gateway to improve data access, the user experience for researchers, and discoverability for data custodians.
- One of the Gateway tools is [Cohort Discovery](#) (formerly known as the [CO-CONNECT tool](#)). This product enables federated querying.
- Cohort Discovery is able to send a query to run against pseudonymised (de-identified) datasets that are hosted, managed, and remain behind the firewall of a data custodian. The query looks for matches to a set of characteristics defined by the user and a numerical response (count) is returned from each dataset showing the number of people in the dataset who meet the characteristics selected. Researchers can then find which data sets are available for their research. The tool uses BC/RQUEST technology, by BC Platforms.

Discussion

- The chair suggested a demo of the Cohort Discovery tool in a future meeting, and that it would also be good to hear about the work to make the onboarding process easier.
- The chair asked members to volunteer to help with the testing of the new Cohort Discovery features.

4. OMOP update – Alex Knight (Project Manager, Data standards)

- The 3rd OMOP special interest group was held on the 9th of February from 2pm-4pm. It was co-chaired by Geoff Hall and Dani-Prieto Alhambra, and it focused on the first OHSDI UK study-a-thon.
- We are looking into training needs for using OMOP/ transforming data set in the UK. We have commenced a survey to explore this need, and we welcome your input on the specifics of what is required: <https://www.surveymonkey.com/r/BX7G9YF>.
- The Chair emphasised that it is possible to participate in international OMOP-based studies with a very minimal number of data items – it is not necessary to OMOP all the data in your organisation. For example, Leeds are currently participating in a European study with cancer centres in 6 countries, and have “OMOPed” only 6 data items. They are then able to examine the impact of COVID on cancer services across 6 European countries.

5. The GA4GH Beacon v2 standard for genomic and clinical data discovery – Tim Beck (University of Nottingham)

[\[Link to Slides: The GA4GH Beacon v2 standard for genomic and clinical data discovery\]](#)

- The [Global Alliance for Genomics and Health](#) (GA4GH) is a worldwide Alliance of data scientists, healthcare practitioners, and genomics researchers. The collaboration has established policy frameworks and technical standards for responsible international use of health and genomics data. It was founded in 2013 and has brought together over 1000 individuals across 90 countries.
- Version 1 of the Beacon API was accepted in 2018 as a GA4GH standard. It is an open standard for genomic data discovery, it answers queries on specific genome variants against individual or aggregate genome collections. A single query can search the 200 data sets that have implemented Beacon v1.
- While Beacon v1 gives information about the presence of mutation in a data set, v2 addresses the needs of clinical research and allows discovery of variants, individuals, cohorts, and biological samples by querying genomic coordinates and/or clinical findings and/or procedural metadata.
- GA4GH would like to understand how Beacon could work with existing HDRUK cohort discovery infrastructure, and how Beacon can work with TREs.

Discussion

- It is on the HDR UK strategic roadmap to work with the federated analytics workstream, to implement this and work with the wider community to enable people to query the UK's health data.
- Discussion is needed to determine whether the specification is documented at a level to support review by disclosure control groups such as SDE airlock committees.

Useful Links:

- Beacon metadata: <http://omop.beacon.bsc.es/api>
- Filters used by the Beacon: http://omop.beacon.bsc.es/api/filtering_terms
- Beacon Query example using clinical codes:
<http://omop.beacon.bsc.es/api/individuals?filters=SNOMED:422650009&filters=LOINC:70274-6>

6. Data Standards and the concept of the Driver Programme Data Design Authority – Monica Jones (University of Leeds).

[\[Link to slide: Data Standards and Design Authority\]](#)

- The [COALESCE study](#), which reveals the impact of COVID-19 vaccination, shows why we need data standards, common data models and meta data description to bring together the work of the four nations through data harmonisation.

- By identifying data priorities, and informing data strategy and quality, we propose to have a convergence of approach by establishing an advisory body, the **Driver Programme Data Design Authority** (DDA) comprising data leads from the Driver programmes and relevant experts.
- The DDA would bring experts with knowledge and experience to address key issues arising from discussions within the Driver Programme teams.
- It is proposed that it will feed into the Data Officer's Group bringing key issues and input.
- Draft Terms of Reference for the group will be finalised and shared.

Discussion

- *What will the data design authority make better and easier?* It's an education and support Opportunity to help Driver Programmes to work in a more efficient and effective way. It will establish a set of data principles to consider when designing studies.
- *Is "Data Design Authority" the best name for the group?* While "Design Authority" is a standard term in large organisations and industry, it's less familiar in academia, and may create the wrong impression. It's important to convey that the group can be influenced by the community; The word "coordination" was mentioned. Suggested alternatives include:
 - "Common Standards Working Group"
 - "Common Standards Advisory Group".
 - "Data Design Authority for Drivers" (DDAD).
- The Data Officer group can influence and shape standards and inform the DDA work, which in the first instance will be guiding/guided by the driver programmes
- Need for clarity of messaging – the name is not important but should not put people off.
- Those people that join the group can input on how it should be developed, specifically the Terms of Reference and the remit of the group.

AOB

- Call for organisations to host interns from the HDRUK Black internship (now closed for 2024, to sign up for 2025 please visit: <https://www.hdruk.ac.uk/study-and-train/about-the-training-team/impact-and-partnerships/an-internship-programme-to-help-talented-black-health-data-scientists-flourish-in-stem-careers/>)
- The next meeting will be held on 8th of May 2024, and we are open to suggestions on speakers and topics for the next meeting.

Attending Organisations

There were 52 attendees from 33 organisations, including:

- HDR UK
- NHS England
- HSCNI
- Barts Health NHS Trust
- INSIGHT HUB
- University of Nottingham
- SAIL Databank
- ICNARC

- CPRD
- Brain Tumour Charity
- Parkinson's UK
- Genomics England
- Research Data Scotland
- NIHR BioResource
- Our Future Health
- University of Leicester
- HQIP
- Discover-NOW
- Imperial College Healthcare NHS Trust
- Cystic Fibrosis Trust
- Imperial College London
- Generation Scotland
- CRUK
- PRSB
- HIC Dundee
- Oxford Health
- Dedalus
- University Hospital Southampton NHS Foundation Trust
- Cardiff University
- Lancashire Teaching Hospitals NHS Trust
- University Hospitals Bristol and Weston NHS Foundation Trust
- University of Edinburgh
- University of Oxford

(Only one organisation listed per attendee – some represented multiple organisations).